

Love is a Basic Need for Human Survival in the short story

‘Kabuliwallah ’

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Abstract:

Rabindranath Tagore is well known Indian English writer. He has tried his hands in variety of forms of literature such as poetry, novel, short stories, essays and dramas. He was versatile personality. The short story *Kabuliwallah* presents the character of Mini. She is a curious girl of five and develops the strong bond of relationship with a stranger Kabuliwallah. Love of Mini, and the narrator support Kabuliwallah and help him to survive. He gets the spiritual love from both of them.

Keywords: *love, human y, survival, unconditional love, care, emotions*

Introduction:

Rabindranath Tagore is well known Indian English writer. He has tried his hands in variety of forms of literature such as poetry, novel, short stories, essays and dramas. He was versatile personality. His writing is full of emotions and sensitivity. His short stories are well acclaimed across the world. Rabindranath Tagore attempted more than ninety short stories. His short stories are known for human values, simplicity, emotional depth and realism. The presentation of need for love is the striking feature of his short stories.

The researcher has selected the *Kabuliwallah* by Rabindranath Tagore for present research paper. Kabuliwallah (Abdul Rahmun) is a dry fruits pedlar from Kabul. He is a poor but honest man. He strongly faces difficulties and challenges of life with a positive approach.. The story moves around the character of Kabuliwallah and Mini. Mini is a curious girl of five and develops the strong bond of relationship with a stranger Kabuliwallah. Mini’s father is a writer who has shared an experience of Mini’s childhood with Kabuliwallah. The short story portrays importance of human relationship and importance of love beyond age, country and

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religion. The story conveys a strong message that love is essential for human survival. Love transcends all the boundaries and barriers. Rabindranth Tagore's characters show love is ultimate truth and that can help us for survival. Mini and Kabuliwallah are representatives of universal love which is essential for the existence of the man and the world.

Analysis:

Kabuliwallah is presented as sensitive and emotional character. He is a pedlar from Kabul and visits each year for selling dry fruits. Kabuliwallah accidentally maintain strong relationship with Mini. When the story begins Mini's father is writing seventieth chapter of the novel and suddenly Mini enters and disturbs her father. She relates her father with the discussion with doorkeeper Ramdayal and Bhola. Mini's father gets angry and sends her outside. The inquisitive nature of Mini creates problem for the narrator to complete his novel. Mini sees Kabuliwallah from the window of her house. Initially she has certain misunderstanding about him. She hides behind her father after calling Kabuliwallah. She believes that there are children in his bag which are kidnapped by him. The children are innocent and they have very fantastic ideas and misconceptions in their minds. "She had a blind belief that inside the bag, which the big man carried, there were perhaps two or three other children like herself" (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 26). Kabuliwallah's daily visits to the narrator's home makes both Mini and Kabuliwallah good friends. They used to talk, play and laugh together. Sometimes Kabuliwallah gives Mini dry fruits or money also freely. The narrator also enjoys the friendship of Kabuliwallah and Mini but mother of Mini is suspicious about the relationship between Mini and Kabuliwallah. She thinks that people like Kabuliwallah are kidnapping or selling the children. They are very dangerous and critical. She says to her husband, "Were children never kidnapped? Was it, then, not true that there was slavery in Kabul? Was it so very absurd that this big man should be able carry off a tiny child?" (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 29). It is a caring love of mother for her daughter. No doubt, her approach is right towards the behaviour of Kabuliwallah.

One day in the middle of January Mini watches the Kabuliwallah who is arrested by the police. The narrator is shocked to see Kabuliwallah, is arrested and in handcuffs. When he enquires about his condition then he gets the detail of his crime. He comes to know that Kabuliwallah has murdered a man due to his refusal to return money. The tender hearted and

innocent girl, Mini asks that Kabuliwallah is going to his in-laws-house (sasural). She curiously asks him, “Are you going to your father-in-law’s house.” (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 31). It is deep kindness and love for Kabuliwallah.

Kabuliwallah is sentenced in imprisonment for a few years and after that he returns. After returning from the jail he immediately goes to the house of Mini. He enquires about Mini to the narrator. The narrator is reluctant to call Mini but the condition of Kabuliwallah encourages him to call Mini. Mini doesn’t recognize Kabuliwallah when she meets him. He thinks that Mini is still a small talkative girl to whom he used to talk before going to jail. When he meets Mini he is shocked to see that Mini is now a young girl. Mini is in a wedding gown. It is unbelievable for him to see her in the wedding gown, sandal paste on her forehead, and adorned as a young bride. She cannot revive their old friendship. “The Kabuliwallah looked a little staggered at the apparition. He could not revive their old friendship.” (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 32) Mini’s wedding costume reminds him, his own daughter. Now, he starts to think that his daughter would have also grown up like Mini. He becomes serious and imagines the wedding day of his daughter. The narrator understands the condition of Kabuliwallah and offers him some money for going to Kabul and meets his own daughter. The narrator is so broadminded and emotional who curtails some expenses on the wedding functions and comes forward to help Kabuliwallah. He thinks himself in the place of Kabuliwallah. A father can understand in a better way to other fathers as is seen through the gesture of the narrator. The narrator believes, “But to me the wedding feast was all the brighter for the thought that in distant land a long lost father met again with his only child.” (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 32).

Love is essential for human survival:

It is believed in all the religions that love is the ultimate truth that can serve as a tonic for human survival. Kabuliwallah’s (Abdul Rahmun) complete survival depends upon the love and affection he receives from Mini. Even Mini’s company takes him away from the worries of life. He forgets even his financial crisis. Mini’s company makes him happy and strong. The narrator says, “They had many quaint jokes, which afforded them much amusement.” (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 26). Even though Kabuliwallah is a poor man but he is very broad by nature who gives raisins and money to Mini. It shows that love for the

stranger girl Mini makes him to take this action. The narrator, Mini's father is a liberal man who doesn't have any objection for the friendship of Mini and Kabuliwallah. Even he tries to convince his wife that Kabuliwallah is not criminal type of man. The narrator believes in the fact that friendship between Mini and Kabuliwallah is based on the pure and unconditional love just like father and daughter. He has firm belief that there is existence of love which is needed for the survival of man.

The doubt of Mini's mother can also be not denied because whatever she feels it is out of her care and worry for Mini. It is a motherly love of Mini's mother that prevents her to easily trust on Kabuliwallah. Mother's love is genuine and ultimate for her children and that essential for the survival of her children and mother as well. She scolds Mini because Mini has taken raisins and money given freely by Kabuliwallah.

Mini is an innocent and sweet girl. Her love for Kabuliwallah is pure and unconditional. Mini's friendship with Kabuliwallah is the source of joy and love for Kabuliwallah. When Mini shouts Kabuliwallah as "O Kabuliwallah, Kabuliwallah, he becomes very happy and thinks that some near and dear one is calling him. Mini's love for Kabuliwallah is just like a daughterly love for father which gives him strength and live long away from his distant land. It is Mini who fills in the absence of Kabuliwallah's daughter in India. Mini's innocent questions, innocent behavior, emotional attachment with him, is kind of love bestowed on Kabuliwallah and that helps him to survive in difficult situation and poverty laden life.

Kabuliwallah is in search of pure love. He loves his daughter but she is long away from him. His daughter Pārbati is always in his mind and that makes him to carry a paper having impression of her hand. The narrator thinks, "He also was a father. That impression of the hand of his little Pārbati in her distant mountain home reminded me of my little Mini." (Tagore *Kabuliwallah*, 32). Father is always father whether he is rich or poor. The narrator realizes the feelings of Kabuliwallah when he sees Kabuliwallah's hand impression on the paper. Mini compensates Kabuliwallah's feelings of love for his daughter. Whenever he is in the company of Mini, he believes that he is with his daughter Pārbati.

Love of Mini, and the narrator support Kabuliwallah and help him to survive. He gets the spiritual love from both of them. The love without the feelings of any return is true love

and that is reflected in the story Kabuliwallah. As Nicholas Sparks states, “The best love is the kind that awakens the soul and makes us reach for more, yet asks for nothing in return.”

Conclusion:

The character of the Kabuliwallah is in search of love. The story presents Kabuliwallah’s need for love is fulfilled by Mini. Love is basic need for the survival of human being. Rabindranth Tagore’s characters show love is ultimate truth and that can helps us for survival. Mini and Kabuliwallah are representatives of universal love which is essential for the existence of the man and the world.

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